

Electric Vehicle Batteries and Thermal Management System

¹. Kunada Naga Venkata Siva, ². Satti Srinivas, ³. Vempatapu Durga Ganesh ⁴. Pamulaparathi Siva Sai Vihar
Sasi Institute of Technology and Engineering

Abstract:- Electric vehicle batteries and other energy storage devices are becoming the increasing the popular. Batteries are working with good performance while maintaining cheap cost, multifunctionality, & facility in hybrid electric vehicles due to their inherent characteristics electric vehicle batteries and designing thermal management system their types, and battery types, are discussed in this overview.

I. INTRODUCTION

During the 1880's "GUSTAVE TROUVE", "THOMAS PARKER" and "ANDREAS FLOCKEN" assembled trial electric vehicles

An electric vehicle battery (EVB, otherwise called a foothold battery) is a battery-powered battery that drives the electric engines of a battery electric vehicle (BEV) or mixture electric vehicle (HEV). They are normally lithium-particle batteries that are explicitly intended for high electric charge (or energy) limit.

Electric vehicle batteries vary from beginning, lighting, and start (SLI) batteries in that they are intended to give capacity to broadened timeframes and are profound cycle batteries.

Since the last part of the 1990s, headways in lithium-particle battery innovation have been driven by versatile gadgets, PCs, telephones, and power apparatuses. These progressions in execution and energy thickness have helped the BEV and HEV markets. In contrast to past battery sciences, for example, nickelcadmium, lithium-particle batteries can be released and re-energized consistently and at any condition of charge. The battery pack represents a huge part of the expense of a BEV or HEV. On each kilowatt-hour premise, the expense of electric vehicle batteries has dropped 87% starting around 2010. To accomplish the ideal voltage and limit in the last pack, an electric vehicle battery is habitually comprised of many little, individual cells organized in a series/equal design. A typical pack is comprised of blocks of 18-30 equal cells that are associated in series to accomplish the ideal voltage. A 400V ostensible pack, for instance, will commonly have around 96 series blocks.

Electric vehicle configuration is a troublesome idea to get a handle on. Here is a glance at the battery, which is at the core of each and every electric vehicle.

The battery is the main part of any electric vehicle (EV). The battery should be intended to meet the prerequisites of the vehicle's motor(s) and charging framework.

II. DESIGNING THE BATTERY THERMAL

➤ *Management System:*

In any system, there are several approaches to designing a battery thermal management system (BTMS). We have provided a systematic way to designing and evaluating a BTMS based on our learning experience.

1. Define the design goal and constraints for the BTMS. The battery type, permissible temperature range, acceptable temperature variance, and vehicle packaging constraints all play a role in this.
2. Determine the heat generation and capacity of the module/pack. These factors will influence the size of the cooling/heating system as well as how quickly the pack reacts to temperature changes.
3. Perform a BTMS and first-order module evaluation. To choose an initial method, preliminary study is undertaken to evaluate the module and pack's transient and steady-state thermal responses. Heat transfer medium possibilities are numerous.
4. Different flow pathways (direct or indirect, series or parallel) and different flow media (air or liquid) are used.
5. Evaluated. We believe that having a good BTMS begins with creating a good Mismodeled that considers thermal behavior.
6. Predict the thermal behavior of the battery module and pack. For both the battery module and the pack, a detailed analysis is performed to assess the influence of various parameters under various situations and driving duty cycles.
7. Make a rough BTMS model. The system parameters are defined based on the packaging and desired performance.

❖ *Batteries Thermal*

➤ *Management System:*

The basic types of BTMS are listed below.

1. Air cooling
2. Liquid cooling
3. Direct refrigerant cooling
4. Phase change material cooling

1. *Air Cooling:*

The air-cooled battery thermal management system (BTMS) is one of the most widely utilised technologies for keeping the battery pack in an electric car at the proper temperature. The cooling efficiency of the aircooled BTMS is improved in this study by optimising the system's flow pattern.

2. *Liquid Cooling:*

It's a cooling system that makes use of water as the coolant to keep the batteries cool. Because of its simple design and effective cooling performance, liquid cooling is the most widely utilised cooling technology. Direct-contact liquid cooling, also known as dielectric liquid cooling, is a liquid that can directly contact the battery cells. mineral oil, for example. The other type is conducting liquid, also known as indirect-contact liquid, which can only make touch with the surface. Indirectly, such as a combination of ethylene glycol and water in battery cells. Depending on the liquids involved, Various layouts have been created.

3. *Direct Refrigerant Cooling:*

A direct refrigerant system (DRS) is similar to an active liquid system in that it has an air conditioning loop, but it employs refrigerant as the heat transfer fluid circulating throughout the battery pack.

4. *Phase Change Material Cooling:*

During the liquefying system, stage change material retains intensity and stores it as idle intensity until it arrives at a greatest worth. The temperature is kept at a softening point for some time, and afterward the increment is deferred. Subsequently, PCM is utilized in the BTMS as a guide and cushion. Likewise, the PCM is constantly blended. utilizing one more BTMS framework to deal with the battery centre, for example, fluid cooling or air-cooling temperature.

❖ *Electrical vehicle batteries types, & its manufacturing companies-*

Ev batteries are stored energy & gives that energy to the moving of vehicle. Batteries are used for the purpose of energy stored, light weight, small in size for our utilization of the moving the electric vehicle **Types of batteries used in electric vehicle-**

Fig 1:- Inner view of battery connection

A. *The Lead-Acid Battery-*

The lead-corrosive battery, which was imagined in 1859, is as yet utilized in numerous vehicles, both burning and electric. The electric vehicle "La Jamais content" ("The Never Happy"), which utilized this innovation, was the primary auto

to surpass 100 km/h in 1899, years before burning motor vehicles.

Lead-corrosive batteries are not generally utilized for footing, but instead to drive the electrical circuit of burning motor adornments or parts like the starter. Regardless of its extensive mass and weight, the lead corrosive battery enjoys the benefit of being both economical and easy to deliver and reuse. It was utilized as the essential energy stockpiling system for electric vehicles until the 1980s, yet it immediately fizzled.

B. *Nickel-Cadmium Battery-*

Assuming that you involved battery-powered batteries during the 1990s, you are now familiar with nickel cadmium innovation. "Ni-Cd" collectors enjoyed various benefits, including high-capacity thickness and a life expectancy of 500 to 1,000 charging cycles.

They did, be that as it may, experience the ill effects of memory impact, an actual peculiarity in which the battery's exhibition debases when exposed to halfway "charge-channel" cycles. Ni-Cd batteries, which were utilized in the development of electric vehicles during the 1990s, are presently denied because of cadmium harmfulness.

C. *Nickel-Metal Hydride Batteries-*

Because of the shortfall of weighty metals, nickel metal hydride (Ni-MH) collectors have seen better progress than Ni-Cd innovation.

Fig 2:- Nickel-metal hydride batteries

This convenient battery-powered battery innovation was the most practical toward the beginning of the 2000s, which is the reason it overwhelmed the crossover vehicle market until the presentation of lithium-particle innovation.

D. *Lithium-Ion Batteries-*

Fig 3:- Lithium-ion Battery

The lithium-particle battery, which was created in the mid-1990s, has progressively set up a good foundation for itself as the main innovation in both the transportation and shopper gadgets enterprises. It has a significantly longer life expectancy than contending innovations, has a lot higher energy thickness, and isn't impacted by the memory impact.

E. *Solid State Battery's* –

Strong state batteries are steadier and more minimized by plan since they don't contain a sloshing, combustible fluid electrolyte. The strong electrolyte can be made of different normal materials, like ceramics and glass.

For a long time, strong state batteries have been utilized in little gadgets like pacemakers, as well as RFID and wearable gadgets. At the point when there are fewer moving parts, there are less things that can turn out badly. Strong state batteries in EVs would give quicker charging times, more prominent travel reach, and, surprisingly, higher energy thickness, notwithstanding further developed wellbeing, size, and security.

Strong state batteries can charge to 80% shortly and are less inclined to strain after various charging cycles. A lithium-particle battery will corrupt after some time.

❖ *Need for electrical batteries* –

On-demand electricity is accepted, stored, and released by batteries and similar devices. Batteries, like many other common energy sources, use chemistry to store energy in the form of chemical potential. For example, logs store energy in their chemical bonds until they are burned and the energy is converted to heat.

❖ *Manufacturing companies for electric vehicle batteries-*

A. *Exide Industries*

Exide Industries Limited, established in 1947, is one of India's driving producers of car and modern leadcorrosive batteries. Exide is the world's fourth biggest producer of such batteries.

The organization has fabricating plants in India and Sri Lanka, and its distributorship traverses 46 nations across five mainland's. Exide Ltd. reuses involved batteries too. As per the organization, the vast majority of the lead delivered in its manufacturing plants is reused after use. The organization's base camp is situated in Kolkata.

B. *Batteries by Amara Raja*

After Exide Industries, Amara Raja Batteries is India's second-largest manufacturer of EV batteries. The company is well-known for its 'Amaron' brand of automotive batteries. Aside from batteries, the company has a presence in a variety of other industries, including packaged foods, beverages, power system production, infrastructure, and so on.

C. *The Tata Group (Tata chemicals)*

The Tata Group has long been a supporter of electric vehicles and green technology, investing and researching in these fields. Tata Motors, Tata Power, Tata Chemicals, and Tata Elxsi, along with their subsidiary companies, plan to

manufacture E-cars that will be completely set up and programmed in-house.

D. *Hero MotoCorp.*

Hero MotoCorp is one of India's and the world's largest manufacturers of two-wheeled vehicles. The company has previously launched E-vehicles.

E. *Maruti Suzuki*

Maruti Suzuki is a Japanese company's subsidiary. It is a major player in the Indian automotive industry. Maruti Suzuki intends to enter the lithium-ion battery manufacturing business through a new joint venture with Toshiba and Denso.

III. CONCLUSION

Taking everything into account, the quick reception of electric vehicles will ascend sooner rather than later, requiring the improvement of additional productive batteries. The warm misfortunes of batteries are one of the most troublesome parts of fostering a predominant BTMS. The EV's reach and responsibility will increase. This paper gives report of different BTMS and different batteries and it are featured to make organizations.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Zhao, R Zhang, S Liu and Gu J 2015 A review of thermal performance improving methods of lithium-ion battery electrode modification and TMS Journal of Power Sources 299 557-577
- [2]. T M Bandhauer, S Garimella and T F Fuller 2011 A Critical review of thermal issues in lithium-ion batteries, J. Electrochem. Soc., 158 R1-R25 1.Zhao, R Zhang, S Liu and Gu J 2015 A review of thermal performance improving methods of lithiumion battery electrode
- [3]. Valeo 2010 Battery Thermal Management for HEV & EV – Technology overview.
- [4]. Kai Chen, Zeyu Li and Shuangfeng Wang 2017 Design of Parallel Air-Cooled Battery Thermal Management System through Numerical Study Energies 10 1677
- [5]. A Pesaran 2002 Battery thermal models for hybrid vehicle simulations Journal of power sources 110 377–82.
- [6]. Pesaran, A.A., Vlahinos, A., Burch, S.D., "Thermal Performance of EV and HEV Battery Modules and Packs," Proceedings of the 14th International Electric Vehicle Symposium, Orlando, Florida, December 15–17, 1997.